

A MODULAR UNIVERSAL DIVIDER FOR CALIBRATION OF UHVDC, AND COMPOSITE WAVES UP TO 1400 KV

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Abstract

With the development of new high voltage cables and switching elements for continuously higher system voltages, especially for HVDC operation, the need for new reference measuring systems for on-site calibration to support activities in type and routine testing. Traceability in testing the fundamental voltage stress, high voltage DC or AC, is superimposed with a Switching or Lightning Impulses has up to now been lacking. This paper describes the design of a new universal RCR divider developed at RISE for a reference measurement system for traceability of ultra-high voltage (UHV) composite and combined waves.

In composite/combined wave measurements the RCR divider is rated 500, 330, 600 and 700 kV for DC, AC_{rms}, Switching Impulse (SI) and Lightning Impulse (LI) respectively. For UHVDC measurements the extended measurement uncertainty is better than 40 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$. In a composite/combined wave measurement, the extended measurement uncertainties for the divider are better than 150 and 400 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ for DC and AC and 0.5% for peak voltage of SI and LI. Two voltage dividers have been built for the purpose to measure both composite and combined waves. This divider is modular, where the HV arms can be stacked to 1000, 660, 1200 and 1400 kV and beyond.

1 Introduction

Electrical energy supply and distribution grids will be subjected to enormous changes as part of the sustainable energy transformation. In the ongoing expansion of the HV power grids, large power plants are replaced by decentralised sources of energy, with new power sources from renewables like large solar and wind parks. Replacing overhead lines with HV cables, and a steadily growing number of rectifiers, inverters and converters puts new demands on grid component testing using superimposed wave shapes.

These voltage stresses are nothing new and have been named composite and combined wave shapes, which originates from the voltage stress of lightning impulse (LI) strikes or events creating switching impulse (SI) on AC or DC power transmission. Composite wave is the stress from ground to any HV conductor and a combined wave is the stress from an impulse and a fundamental across e.g., an open circuit breaker.

These combined or composite voltage tests are carried out in the test laboratories without proper support by metrological traceability and standardisation relying on single stress measurements and calculation. An EU funded project was started, named EMPIR 19NRM07 HV-com² [1], with the aim to resolve and provide traceable measurements of voltages for composite and combined tests and give input to standardisation [2]. This project has developed three HV dividers, various software from partners for evaluation of parameters and LV traceability for the wave shapes.

Furthermore, calibration services for UHVDC are not available above 1000 kV. There is a need to extend the calibration capabilities for voltage instrument transformers up to 1200 kV and for factory component testing capabilities up to 2000 kV. To support testing laboratories for UHVDC, now approaching 2000 kV, the EU funded project EMPIR 19ENG02 FutureEnergy [3] aims to extend the traceable calibration of Ultra-High Voltage Direct Current (UHVDC) up to at least 1600 kV, possibly 2000 kV.

To support both projects, an internal funding by RISE was used to build a measurement system based on a new design of a universal RCR voltage divider, a commercial transient recorder, and the development of a new evaluation software. The divider design, presented in this paper, is rated 500/330/600/700 kV for DC, AC_{rms}, SI and LI respectively. Two dividers have been built for measurement of combined waves. The divider is modular, so using the HV arm from one divider and stack it on top of the other, extends the range to 1000, 660, 1000 and 1400 kV.

In contrast to the optimization criteria of the universal divider designed in 19NRM07 [1], using a special selection of resistors for this divider it now also supports the UHVDC calibration of 19ENG02 [3]. By optimization of the mechanical design for easy on-site assessment the original target of 400 kV has been extended to 500 kV. This new modular RCR divider can extend the voltage range beyond the recently extended precision shielded modular RCRC type

1200 kV UHVDC divider [2]. PTB has in this context of UHVDC calibration developed an alternative RCRC UHVDC divider to reach 1600 kV and beyond [3].

2. Design of the HV divider

2.1 System properties

The measurement system target voltage rating for the universal RCR divider was 400 kV DC/AC_{peak}/SI and LI. This divider is designed to be fitted on rollers and limited to a total height below 240 cm for easy loading on a truck used for on-site calibration. The divider shall be built using standard off-shelf components and have as high capacitance as possible to minimize proximity effects. The components shall withstand at least 400 kV of any stress, and it shall have as low inductance as possible to be fast enough for LI calibration. The final design has the following properties:

- HV capacitance – 250 pF
- HV resistance – 2 GΩ.
- HV damping factor – 4.0 (Eq. 1)
- Settling time – 135 μs (important for LI)
- Voltage rating – 500/330(rms)/600/700 kV (DC, AC, SI and LI)

The rating is limited by one of the following three considerations: 1) components ratings, 2) internal insulation by multiphysics calculations and measurements on the support structure material, and 3) external insulation (Fig. 1 and 2).

Fig. 1: Modeling of electric field of an RCR500 divider.

The external insulation limits are plotted for voltage stresses given in Fig. 2. Four different divider configurations using e to four HV modules are covered in the plot.

Up to date two HV modules have been built, i.e., an RCR1000 configuration. Adding a third module for on-site calibration of UHVDC up to 1600 kV would then be possible. The external insulation coordination of Fig. 2 is very conservative, which limits SI for two modules to 1000 kV. Further studies and tests will aim for increasing the limit.

Fig. 2: Insulation coordination and divider heights for different voltage stresses and divider sizes. RCR500 -- 1.9 m, RCR1000 -- 3.9 m, RCR1500 -- 6.0 m and RCR2000 -- 8.1 m.

2.2 System schematic

In the first design the divider has a scale factor (SF) of 2000:1 which gives 250 – 350 V at the output of the LV arm. Further attenuation of the signal is made an RCR attenuator close to the transient recorder, which has a SF of 50:1. The system has now a total SF of 100 000:1, giving 5 – 7 V at the recorder input. For precision UHVDC measurements a special LV arm was designed for precision UHVDC calibration with a SF of 50 000:1 for a RCR500 or 100 000:1 for a RCR1000 configuration. These SF use the 10 V range of the Agilent 3458A multimeter optimally. A schematic of the measurement system for composite wave measurement is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: A schematic of the divider and attenuator.

2.3 Architecture

To minimize the inductance, a meandering path was chosen shown in Fig. 4. This makes the design compact and reduces the mutual inductance in the HV arm.

Fig. 4: The current flow in the HV stack

The components were mounted on 3D printed disks of PLA plastics, each supporting six WIMA FKP 1 capacitors (Red in Fig. 5), six Caddock TF050R bleeders (White in Fig. 5) and three Ohmite OX type damping resistors (Light green in Fig. 5). 100 of these disks were stacked and mounted inside an FRP tube, sealed, evacuated, and backfilled with SF₆ (Fig. 7) With the protective gas the divider is immune to humidity, which typically has a time constant around 10 days, which has also improved the HV field insulation.

Fig. 5: Mounting of components on 3D printed PLA disks. Red WIMA FKP1 capacitors, white Caddock TF050R precision bleeder resistors and green Ohmite OX damping resistors.

The LV arm has a coaxial mounting of the capacitors and damping resistors connected to a mounting bar and a precision resistor with termination resistors mounted close to a 50 Ω connector type LEMO 4 The low voltage arm has a coaxial structure for the capacitance and damping resistors with the precision resistor on a same board (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: An open LV arm with a coaxial mounting of capacitors and dampening resistors and a precision resistor with termination on the small board.

2.2 Component selection

For UHVDC precision measurement, a similar precision type resistors from Caddock were chosen, as used in another modular HVDC divider design [3, 5]. These resistors were of the type Caddock TF050R, 3.33 MΩ, 0.1%, TC=15 ppm/K, VC=20 ppm/kV and max voltage 1400 V. The TF050R is the forerunner to the USF370 used in the HVDC divider. Polypropylene metallized foil pulse capacitors from WIMA were selected type FKP1, 150 nF 1250/600 V, 11 kV/μs. The capacitors have a large temperature coefficient, typically -300 ppm/K and are also voltage dependent. The choice of damping resistors, both internal and front resistor, was a ceramic composition from Ohmite, type OX, with a TC=1000 ppm/K.

Using the same components in both the HV arm and front resistor as in the LV arm, the voltage divider is compensated for the high TC. To minimize the influence of voltage coefficients, a recent modification of the divider (Fig. 3), using a scale factor of 600 instead of 2000 eliminates the VC. With the same SF as the number of components in the HV stack, the voltage divider on each component experiences the same voltage in both the HV and LV arm eliminating the VC. This further reduce AC, SI and LI measurement uncertainties.

Fig. 7: A full stack of 100 disks before closing the structure (left) and a complete divider (right).

The front resistor was designed and built using the same Ohmite OX resistors for the damping of the divider. A rule of thumb is to use an optimum damped design with a factor of 2 in Eq. 1, where R_{tot} is the total damping in the HV arm. With the measured inductance of the HV arm (section 3.2) and the contribution from size of the loop to the common point in an LI calibration, i.e., 4.8 μH an optimally damping with $k=2$ would need $R_{tot} = 600 \Omega$.

$$R_{tot} = k \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}} = k \sqrt{\frac{22.3 \cdot 10^{-6}}{251 \cdot 10^{-12}}} = k \cdot 300 \Omega \quad (1)$$

Before deciding on the damping of the divider, not having balanced the inductance in the divider, the upper bandwidth is determined by Eq. 2.

$$f = \frac{L}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot R_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

In this design we have chosen a damping factor $k = 4$. With these values we have the cross-over frequencies for DC to AC operation at 0.3 Hz, well removed from the 50 Hz AC, one cross-over between capacitive divider and damping resistance divider is 530 kHz from $(1/2 \cdot \pi \cdot R_d C)$ and the upper bandwidth determined by Eq. 2 is 8.5 MHz, above which the divider is unbalanced inductively.

The voltage stress across the front resistor was estimated for tail chopped impulses using LTSpice and is about 160 kV. With the OX type resistors, with U_{max} 14 kV and E_{max} 50 J, using 12 in series the resistors will be at the voltage limit. These were later replaced with 11 in series of the OY type with U_{max} 20 kV and E_{max} 80 J. The maximum energy uptake with the longest LI half time value of 60 μ s is 650 J. In the design there are 6 resistors in parallel in each stage and 11 in series, giving only 0.7 J per resistor to absorb.

3. Characterisation

3.1 Components

All components and especially the capacitors and damping resistors were characterised for temperature and voltage.

3.2 HV and LV arm

The inductance was determined a Wayne-Kerr LCR bridge for both a submodule (10 disks) and the assembled HV arm. A resonance was found close to the limit of the instrument, which is 3 MHz, which gives an inductance of 17.5 μ H. The coaxial structure of the LV arm is characterized in the same way.

3.4 Divider

The temperature dependencies of the full divider were measured with a calibrator applying 1 kV and measuring the SF from 10 to 30 °C. For DC the TC is 2 ppm/K and for AC it is 7 ppm/K. The capacitance of the HV and LV arms were determined using a Guildline 9910 bridge at HV and LV. The 17.5 μ H inductance of the HV arm gives a total inductance in an LI calibration of ca 22 μ H.

3.5 Step response

To check that the dividing ratio is balanced between the capacitive and damping resistors, the divider step response is measured using a mercury whetted relay [6]. The front resistor is then tuned to have as fast settling time as possible [6] or minimizing the front time error after convolution with a LI wave shape as described in section 4.4.

4. Calibration of the divider

4.1 DC calibration

The DC scale factor is determined by calibration against the modular HVDC divider [7]. There are two LV arms for the system, one precision LV_{DC} with scale factor 50000:1 or 100 000:1 for a 500 or 1000 kV configuration, and one LV_C for composite wave measurements with scale factor 100 000:1

using the 50:1 attenuator. For precision DC measurements with, Table 1 shows the uncertainty assessment for a DC measurement, with an expanded uncertainty – 40 μ V/V.

Table 1 Uncertainty for 1000 kV precision DC

Contribution	Standard unc.	Unit
SF calibration vs UHVDC	10.00	ppm
Uncertainty of voltage coefficient	1.00	μ V/V
Uncertainty of temp coefficient	0.10	μ V/V
Uncertainty for (23 ± 5) °C	5.00	μ V/V
Non-linearity due to leakage currents	1.00	μ V/V
Self-heating effect + VC	12.00	μ V/V
DMM reading + range Agilent 3458A	2.15	μ V/V
Short term stability	0.10	μ V/V
Long term stability	0.15	μ V/V
Statistical spread	4.86	μ V/V
Total standard uncertainty	17.30	μ V/V
Expanded uncertainty (k=2)	34.60	μV/V

4.2 AC calibration

The divider AC scale factor was calibrated up to full AC voltage against AC divider based on a Haefely NK300 gas capacitor. This SF was checked against a calculated SF using a Guildline 9910 bridge. The HV capacitance and LV capacitance was measured with contribution of stray capacitance in the divider, e.g., HV arm from toroid to bottom plate. Both methods show a SF linearity error of -0.026 /kV which gives -0.08% at 320 kV.

4.3 LI and SI impulse

In the composite wave configuration, i.e., the divider plus the 50:1 attenuator, the scale factor for a 500 kV configuration is 100 000:1. This scale factor is based on the AC calibration. The uncertainty assessment is given by the parameters in IEC 60060-2 [2]. The assessment of measurement uncertainty contributions which now follows is described in detail elsewhere [8] but is adapted to the properties of the RCR system.

4.3.1 Scale factor

For AC and impulse measurement, the AC scale factor is determined at HV without the front resistor R_d present in the circuit. The contribution to standard uncertainty is denoted u_{ref} . Time parameter errors are determined by step response and convolution with nominal waveshapes with known parameters. The contribution to standard uncertainty is denoted u_{ref} .

4.3.2 Linearity

The linearity is determined by comparison with two resistive dividers, for which the non-linearity has been determined though comparison with other dividers of similar rating, but with different technologies. This method gives a much more conservative estimate and catches contributions from the damping resistors and transient recorder, which is why u_{B1} in Table 2 is 2.5 times higher than the linearity from AC calibration.

4.3.3 Dynamic behaviour

The response of the divider is determined in conditions representative of its use, particularly clearances to earthed and energized structures. This is analysed by step response as described in section 4.4.

4.3.4 Short term stability

The maximum voltage of the assigned measurement range was applied ten times to the divider at the assigned rate of 2 impulses per minute. The scale factor was measured as soon as possible after the impulse series.

4.3.5 Long term stability

Using data from former measurements provides information if the impulse divider changes with time. The stability is estimated as an uncertainty contribution valid for a projected time of use.

4.3.6 Temperature dependence

A linear approximation of the temperature dependence of the scale factor is used to estimate the change in scale factor with temperature. The divider was put into a climate chamber and the temperature was varied from 10 to 30 °C.

4.3.5 Temperature dependence

Keeping the measurement circuit constant and varying the distance to objects in the vicinity or changing the distance between the divider and the measurement point shows how sensitive the divider is to proximity effects. Convolution of step responses is used as a tool to find the difference and finding an uncertainty estimate.

4.4 Step response

By registering step responses, as shown in Fig. 8, the step is convolved with a LI wave shape and the errors of all LI parameters are analysed. The T_1 error is then tuned to a minimum by trimming the resistance of the front resistor R_d .

Fig. 8 A sample step response of the divider.

Now the divider step response is measured for different distances, 0.5H, 1H and 2H where H is the height of the divider and 1H is the tuned distance to common point at a calibration. This is performed against a grounded wall and with the step generator mounted at a common point.

4.5 Impulse uncertainties

All data of uncertainties from section 4.3 are now collected as in Table 2, which gives the divider contribution to a

measurement system. In summary the divider contributes with about 0.5% to all parameters.

Table 2 Uncertainty for LI 0.84/60 μ s from IEC 60060-2

Contribution to standard uncertainty	U_p [%]	T_1 [%]	T_2 [%]
u_{ref}	0.015	0.250	0.250
Linearity u_{B1}	0.229	0.000	0.000
Dynamic u_{B2}	0.006	0.018	0.018
Short term u_{B3}	0.006	0.000	0.000
Long term u_{B4}	0.003	0.000	0.000
Temperature u_{B5}	0.003	0.000	0.000
Proximity u_{B6}	0.007	0.012	0.012
Total std. uncertainty	0.230	0.251	0.251
Expanded unc. (k=2)	0.459	0.502	0.502

5. Intercomparisons

The RISE system took part in two intercomparisons: 1) an UHVDC calibration at an open test area at PTB, 2) a composite wave intercomparison campaign at PTB.

5.2 UHVDC campaign

Four dividers were compared in a measurement campaign at PTB (Figure 9). The upgraded shielded precision modular 1200 kV UHVDC divider of RISE was used as reference. The expanded measurement uncertainty for the reference is 20 μ V/V [7].

Fig. 9 Intercomparison between PTB 1200 kV divider (1), RISE 1200 kV divider (2), PTB generator 2000 kV (3), PTB 2000 kV divider (4) and RISE 1000 kV universal divider (5).

Table I gives the scale factor and expanded measurement uncertainty for the universal divider. Corona from the generator and 1600 kV divider was present in the circuit above 600 kV which drives the standard deviation. Hence, the scale factor of the unshielded RCR divider is 99906.5 with an expanded measurement uncertainty of 27 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ using the data up to 600 kV and the scale factor from all data. Under controlled conditions the UHVDC measurement uncertainty of the universal divider, given the facts from the uncertainty estimate in Table 2 and the stability of the scale factor values, is 40 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$.

Table 3 Calibration summary of universal divider

U [kV]	SF error [$\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$]	k	v_{eff}	Exp unc.
100	-3.4	2.0	110	± 0.0026
200	-0.4	2.0	110	± 0.0026
400	4.2	2.0	160	± 0.0029
600	3.3	2.0	150	± 0.0028
800	-1.4	2.0	70	± 0.0073
1000	-2.2	2.0	100	± 0.0205
Average	0.4			
Exp. unc. (k=2)	3.3			± 0.0028

Fig. 2 Plot of data from Table 1.

5.1 Composite wave

Using three different measurement systems, traceability and calibration services for composite and combined waveforms were developed and set up by the participating national metrology institutes at PTB in June 2022. The results and parameters were reported to the ongoing revision of the IEC 60060 series [2]

Fig 9: A recorded 100 kV composite wave SI on 15 kV AC.

The parameters to be determined is discussed within IEC TC42 [2] and a separate paper describes these.

6. Conclusion

This universal RCRC divider covers the need from both projects [1,3] enabling both UHVDC and composite/combined wave calibration. The unshielded universal divider has proven to be remarkably stable capable of both UHVDC measurements with an expanded measurement uncertainty of 40 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$. An extended measurement uncertainties for the divider used for composite and combined wave are better than 150 and 400 $\mu\text{V}/\text{V}$ for DC and AC and the contribution to impulse parameters from this divider including the attenuator is 0.5% for U_p , T_1 and T_2 .

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8 References

- [1] EMPIR 19NRM07 HV-com²:
<https://www.ptb.de/empir2020/hv-com2/home/>, accessed 10 March 2023.
- [2] IEC 60060-2: 'High-Voltage Test Techniques - Part 2: Measuring systems', 2011IEC TC42, 60060-2, 2010
- [3] EMPIR 19ENG02 FutureEnergy:
<https://www.ptb.de/empir2020/futureenergy/home/> , accessed 10 March 2023.
- [4] Frank Gerdinand, Johann Meisner, Stephan Passon et.al. New Reference UHVDC Divider for the Calibration of Testing Equipment up to 1600 kV”, Submitted to ISH 2023.
- [5] EMRP ENG07 HVDC “Metrology for high voltage direct current” 2010 – 2013, <https://www.euramet.org/research-innovation/search-research-projects/details/project/metrology-for-high-voltage-direct-current>
- [6] A. Bergman, M. Nordlund, A-P. Elg et. al. “Characterisation of a fast step Generator”, ISH 2017, 20th International Symposium on High Voltage, Buenos Aires, Argentina, Aug 27 – Sept 01, 2017, paper 484.
- [7] J. Hällström A. Bergman, S. Dedeoğlu et. al. “Performance of a modular wideband 1000 kV HVDC reference divider”; CPEM 2014, Aug 24 – 29, Rio de Janeiro
- [8] “Characterisation at Low Voltage of Two Reference Lightning Voltage Dividers”, ISH 2017, 20th International Symposium on High Voltage, Buenos Aires, Argentina, Aug 27 – Sept 01, 2017. paper 485.